

**INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT): DRIVER AND
ENABLER OF 21ST CENTURY LITERACY**

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Abstract

In times past, Literacy was viewed simply as ‘the ability to read, write and understand simple sentences. As good as this sounds, it is no longer acceptable as a result of the wide dimensions that literacy has assumed in recent times with the emergence of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) which has imparted the ‘knowledge industry’ in diverse ways. There is, as it is now, little or no demarcation between the two words ‘Literacy and Education’ in the 21st century, the reason for this is not farfetched, ICT is the major factor if not the only one responsible for expanding the frontiers of Literacy from just providing information for people to swallow to mind opening enlightenment beyond what the teacher can give to enabling recipients contribute meaningfully, analyze, criticize and equipped with contemporary skills which makes an individual not just a complete personality but a global citizen.

This paper also juxtaposed the literacy rate in Nigeria with those of some countries in Europe and other African countries to assess the country’s weak points as well as proffer solutions that will move Nigeria’s literacy rate upwards.

Keywords: Literacy, Education, ICT, Integration, 21st Century Skills.